

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Longitudinal Patterns of Fatigue in Long-Term Survivors of Childhood and Adolescent Cancers: A Report From the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study

Salome Christen¹

¹Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland | ²Cancer Registry Bern Solothurn, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland | ³Division of General Pediatrics, Pediatric Hematology and Oncology Unit, Department of Pediatrics, Gynecology and Obstetrics, University Hospitals of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland | ⁴Department of Pediatrics, Gynecology and Obstetrics, CANSEARCH Research Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland | ⁵Division of Pediatric Hematology/Oncology, Department of Pediatrics, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland | ⁶Cantonal Hospital Baselland, University Institute of Internal Medicine, Liestal, Switzerland | ⁷Childhood Cancer Research Group, Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland | ⁸Division of Paediatric Oncology/Haematology, University Children's Hospital Basel, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

Correspondence: Gisela Michel (gisela.michel@unilu.ch)

Received: 26 July 2025 | **Revised:** 24 September 2025 | **Accepted:** 24 September 2025

Funding: The SCCSS was supported by the Swiss Cancer League and Swiss Cancer Research (KLS-3644-02-2015, KFS-4722-02-2019, KLS/KFS-482501-2019, KLS/KFS-5711-01-2022, KFS-6105-02-2024), Kinderkrebshilfe Schweiz (www.kinderkrebshilfe.ch), Kinderkrebs Schweiz (www.kinderkrebs-schweiz.ch) and Stiftung für krebskranke Kinder - Regio Basiliensis (<https://www.stiftung-kinderkrebs.ch>). The data collection of the general population was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (100019_153268 / 1). S.C. has received funding from Vontobel-Stiftung, Krebsliga Zentralschweiz, and Avenir Stiftung.

Keywords: childhood cancer | fatigue | longitudinal | registry | survivorship | Switzerland

ABSTRACT

Background: Fatigue negatively affects quality of life. We aimed to compare the prevalence of fatigue in survivors of childhood cancer with the Swiss general population, describe longitudinal patterns of fatigue, and identify characteristics associated with persistent fatigue in survivors.

Procedure: In this cohort study, we used data from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry and the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study, including survivors (≥ 5 years since diagnosis; diagnosed between 1976 and 2015 at < 20 years of age) aged ≥ 20 years at study entry, using data from the baseline and follow-up survey. A representative sample of the general population was used as a comparison group. *Fatigue prevalence* and *fatigue severity* were measured using the SF-36 vitality scale, from which we derived longitudinal patterns (*no/low fatigue*, *late onset*, *improving*, *persistent*). We used multivariable logistic regression to identify clinical, psychosocial and demographic characteristics associated with *persistent fatigue*.

Results: Overall, 1846 survivors participated at baseline (52% male), and 684 survivors also participated at follow-up (median 9 years from baseline; 52% male). From the general population, 863 persons participated (42% male). Survivors had similar *fatigue prevalence* at baseline/follow-up (26%/29%) as the general population (26%). *No/Low fatigue* was experienced by 64%, *late onset* by

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; BSI-18, Brief Symptom Inventory-18; CNS, central nervous system; IQR, interquartile range; OR, odds ratio; SCCSS, Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study; SF-36, Short Form-36; SMN, second malignant neoplasm.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC. This article has been contributed to by U.S. Government employees and their work is in the public domain in the USA.

14%, *improving* by 7%, and *persistent fatigue* by 15% of survivors. More late effects, psychological distress, pain, and less time spent on moderate-intensity physical activity were associated with *persistent fatigue*.

Conclusions: This study provides data on longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors and identifies factors associated with persistent fatigue that can be used to identify survivors at risk and as a target for interventions aimed at improving fatigue.

1 | Introduction

Fatigue is prevalent among survivors of childhood and adolescent cancers, and significantly impacts survivors' functioning and quality of life [1–3]. Cancer-Related fatigue is defined by the National Comprehensive Cancer Network as a 'distressing, persistent, subjective sense of physical, emotional and/or cognitive tiredness or exhaustion related to cancer or cancer treatment that is not proportional to recent activity and interferes with usual functioning' [4]. Fatigue negatively affects participation in activities of daily life [2, 5], working ability [6], and quality of life [2] in survivors. At the same time, it is often difficult for survivors with persisting fatigue to get their symptoms and condition recognised [7] or to obtain financial support from health or disability insurances [4].

More than 50% of patients experience fatigue during treatment for childhood and adolescent cancers [8, 9], and during treatment, fatigue is perceived as the most severe and interfering symptomatic adverse effect by children and adolescents affected by cancer [10]. Fatigue generally improves after treatment [11], but many survivors experience fatigue in the long-term [1, 3, 12]. In a previous systematic review, we found that the prevalence of fatigue in survivors ranges from 10% to 85% [1], but limited data are available from Switzerland [3].

The longitudinal patterns of fatigue in long-term survivors (≥ 5 years) of childhood and adolescent cancer are unclear, and several studies have called for research that clarifies the course of fatigue [1, 4, 11]. Four studies have investigated longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors of childhood cancer around treatment end [11, 13–15]. Fewer studies have investigated this in long-term survivors: A Norwegian study found that, in 5-year survivors of lymphomas and leukaemia, 31% of survivors were persistently fatigued [16]. A Dutch study in brain tumour survivors found that cognitive fatigue worsened over time, whereas general fatigue first improved, then worsened [17]. However, both studies focused on selected diagnostic groups. As fatigue can occur after any type of cancer [1], it is relevant to assess longitudinal patterns for all diagnoses.

We used data from a nationwide, population-based cohort study, the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study (SCCSS) [18], to (a) compare prevalence and severity of fatigue in survivors to the general population, (b) describe longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors, and (c) identify characteristics associated with persistent fatigue in survivors.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Study Population and Procedure

2.1.1 | Survivor Population

The Childhood Cancer Registry (<https://www.childhoodcancerregistry.ch/>) is a nationwide, population-based cancer registry for all Swiss residents diagnosed younger than 20 years of age with leukaemia, lymphoma, central nervous system (CNS) tumours, malignant solid tumours or Langerhans cell histiocytosis since 1976 [19]. The SCCSS is a nationwide, population-based, prospective cohort study including all children and adolescents registered in the Childhood Cancer Registry who survived at least 5 years since diagnosis (<https://www.swiss-ccss.ch/en/>) [18]. For the current analysis, we included survivors aged ≥ 20 years at study entry because of a different survey version used for younger survivors.

A detailed description of the SCCSS is provided elsewhere [18]. In short, survivors first received a letter from their former treatment centre with study information and the option to refuse participation. Two weeks later, the SCCSS research team at the University of Bern sent survivors a paper-based questionnaire with a pre-paid return envelope. If they did not respond, they received a reminder letter with another questionnaire 4–6 weeks later. Non-responding survivors were contacted by phone for a second reminder. Baseline data were collected from 2007 to 2022, with an overall response rate of 56%. Follow-up data were collected from 2016 to 2022 from participants who had completed the baseline survey (response rate of the follow-up questionnaire 53%).

2.1.2 | General Population

Previously, our group collected health-related data from a random and representative sample of the Swiss general population in the context of another study [20, 21]. The sample was obtained from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office. It was drawn according to the representative distribution of age, sex and language region in Switzerland and included 3000 households ($n = 7052$ persons). Household members were eligible if they were aged 18–75 years in 2015 ($n = 5644$ eligible persons). They were contacted individually by postal mail from May 2015 to June 2016. Overall, 1255 persons participated in the survey (response rate 24%). For the current

analysis, we restricted the sample to participants within the same age range as the survivor population (aged ≥ 20 and < 60 years at study).

2.2 | Measurements

2.2.1 | Fatigue

Fatigue was measured with the vitality scale of the Short Form-36 (SF-36) Version 2 [22]. The SF-36 vitality scale is a reliable and valid measure of fatigue [23], is sensitive to change [23], and has been validated and successfully used in survivors of childhood cancer [24]. Participants were asked, 'How much of the time during the past 4 weeks (a) ... have you felt full of life?'; '(b) ... did you have a lot of energy?'; '(c) ... did you feel worn out?'; and '(d) ... did you feel tired?'. Participants could choose from a five-point Likert scale ranging from 'never' to 'all of the time'. We scored the SF-36 and subscales according to the scoring manual [25], and generated standardised scores ranging from 0 to 100. Lower scores on the SF-36 vitality scale indicate greater fatigue (*fatigue severity*). Scores ≤ 45 have been established as representing clinically significant fatigue [26]. We generated a caseness variable for *fatigue prevalence*, with participants scoring ≤ 45 as having fatigue. We generated longitudinal fatigue patterns based on *fatigue prevalence* at baseline and follow-up: *no/low fatigue* (no fatigue at baseline and follow-up), *late-onset fatigue* (no fatigue at baseline, fatigue at follow-up), *improving fatigue* (fatigue at baseline, no fatigue at follow-up), and *persistent fatigue* (fatigue at baseline and follow-up). The SF-36 was administered twice to the SCCSS participants (at baseline and follow-up), and once to the general population.

2.2.2 | Explanatory Variables

We obtained prospectively collected information from the Childhood Cancer Registry: sex (male, female), cancer diagnosis (according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer - third edition) [27], and recoded into the major tumour groups (leukaemia, lymphoma, CNS tumours, other tumours), surgery (yes/no), chemotherapy (yes/no), radiotherapy (yes/no), stem cell transplantation (yes/no), relapse or second malignant neoplasm (SMN; yes/no), age at diagnosis (years), and year of diagnosis (1976–2015, 10-year increments).

The following data were assessed at baseline in the SCCSS: health status (good–excellent, fair–poor), any late effects (yes, no), organ-specific late effects (yes, no; assessed for neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive or urinary system), number of organ systems affected by late effects (range = 0–9), psychological distress (T-score ≥ 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory [BSI]-18) [20, 28, 29] pain (none–mild, moderate–very severe), body mass index (BMI), time spent on vigorous-intensity physical activity (in half hours per week), time spent on moderate-intensity physical activity (in half hours per week), year of study participation (year), age at study (years), language region (German, French, Italian), migration background (yes, no), civil status (single, married, widowed/divorced), highest educational achievement (compulsory school, vocational

training, upper secondary education, university education), and employment situation (employed, unemployed, in education). We generated time since diagnosis (years) by subtracting age at diagnosis (years) from age at baseline (years), and time to follow-up (years) by subtracting age at baseline (years) from age at follow-up (years). A more detailed description of the coding of the explanatory variables can be found in [Appendix 1](#).

For the general population, the following data were assessed through self-report: sex, age at study, language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement and employment situation.

2.3 | Data Analysis

For all analyses, we used Stata Statistical Software: Release 18. We excluded participants with incomplete information in the SF-36 vitality scale (survivors: $n = 117$ [6%] at baseline, $n = 7$ [1%] at follow-up; general population: $n = 7$ [1%]) and analysed available cases (pairwise deletion).

Aim A: We used descriptive statistics to describe the *fatigue prevalence* and *fatigue severity* in survivors and the general population. We used logistic regression to test for differences in *fatigue prevalence* between survivors and the general population, and linear regression to test for differences in *fatigue severity* between survivors and the general population, adjusting for sex, age and socio-demographic characteristics (language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement and employment situation).

Aim B: We only included survivors who participated in both the baseline and follow-up questionnaires. We calculated the proportion of survivors with specific longitudinal fatigue patterns: *no/low fatigue* (no fatigue at baseline and follow-up), *late onset fatigue* (no fatigue at baseline, fatigue at follow-up), *improving fatigue* (fatigue at baseline, no fatigue at follow-up), and *persistent fatigue* (fatigue at baseline and follow-up). We used <https://sankeymatic.com/> to build Figure 1.

Aim C: In survivors participating in both the baseline and follow-up questionnaire, we used univariable and multivariable logistic regression to identify characteristics associated with *persistent fatigue* (reference group: *no/low fatigue*). We included independent variables (measured at baseline) that were associated with fatigue in previous studies [1, 3, 15, 30–33]: cancer diagnosis, surgery, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, stem cell therapy, relapse/SMN, time since diagnosis, health status, organ-specific late effects, number of late effects, psychological distress, pain, BMI, vigorous-intensity physical activity, moderate-intensity physical activity, age at study, sex, civil status and employment situation. We a priori included age at diagnosis, year of diagnosis, educational achievement, and year of study participation as independent variables. In the multivariable model, we ran a full model, only excluding covariables that were correlated with others, or categorical covariables that had a cell size of $n < 25$.

3 | Results

We included 1846 survivors with baseline information (52% male, 48% female). Of the survivors invited to participate in

FIGURE 1 | Longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer participating in both the baseline and follow-up survey ($N = 684$). *Note:* The numbers in the boxes indicate the number and proportion of survivors with fatigue at baseline and follow-up, and the number and proportion of survivors with the distinct longitudinal fatigue patterns: no/low fatigue (no fatigue at baseline and follow-up), late-onset fatigue (no fatigue at baseline, fatigue at follow-up), improving fatigue (fatigue at baseline, no fatigue at follow-up), and persistent fatigue (fatigue at baseline and follow-up).

the follow-up survey, 684 survivors (52% male, 48% female) responded to the follow-up questionnaire. From the general population, we included 863 participants (42% male, 58% female). At baseline, survivors were on average 26.8 years old (interquartile range [IQR] 9.9 years) and 18.0 years from diagnosis (IQR 12.5 years). At follow-up, survivors were on average 36.7 years old (IQR 9.5), 8.9 years from the baseline survey (IQR 4.1), and 28.8 years from diagnosis (IQR 10.4). Participants of the general population were on average 43.7 years old (IQR 16.9) (Table 1).

Fatigue prevalence was similar in survivors at baseline (26%) and follow-up (29%), and the general population (26%; Table 1). After adjusting for sex, age and socio-demographic characteristics, we did not find any differences in *fatigue prevalence* between the general population and survivors at baseline (odds ratio [OR] = 0.9, 95% CI: 0.7–1.2), or follow-up (OR = 1.0, 95% CI: 0.7–1.3; Tables S1 and S2).

Fatigue severity was similar in survivors at baseline (mean 50.2, SD 10.8) and follow-up (mean 49.0, SD 10.9), and the general population (mean 49.3, SD 10.2; Table 1). After adjusting for sex, age and socio-demographic characteristics, we found that the score for *fatigue severity* was slightly higher in survivors at baseline than in the general population ($b = 1.2$, 95% CI: 0.1–2.2; indicating less fatigue symptoms in survivors), and we found no differences between survivors at follow-up and the general population ($b = 0.2$, 95% CI: –1.1 to 1.5; Tables S3 and S4). *Fatigue prevalence* and *fatigue severity* stratified by participants' characteristics are presented in Tables S5 and S6.

On an individual level, 64% ($n = 437$) of survivors had consistently *low or no fatigue*, 14% ($n = 93$) had *late-onset fatigue*, 7% ($n = 49$) had *improving fatigue*, and 15% ($n = 105$) experienced *persistent fatigue* (Figure 1, Table S7).

Experiencing late effects in a greater number of organ systems (OR = 1.5, 95% CI: 1.2–1.9), psychological distress (OR = 14.5, 95% CI: 5.9–35.6), and pain (OR = 6.1, 95% CI: 2.1–17.9) was associated with a higher likelihood of experiencing *persistent fatigue*. In

contrast, more time spent on moderate-intensity physical activity (half hours per week; OR = 0.95, 95% CI: 0.9–1.0) was associated with a lower likelihood of experiencing *persistent fatigue* (Table 2).

The results from the univariable analysis are presented in Table S8.

4 | Discussion

Around one in four survivors (26%) experienced fatigue, which was comparable to the general population. Most survivors (64%) experienced *low or no fatigue*, 14% had *late-onset fatigue*, 7% had *improving fatigue*, and 15% experienced *persistent fatigue*. More late effects, psychological distress, pain and spending less time on moderate-intensity physical activity were associated with *persistent fatigue*.

Fatigue is a significant problem in long-term survivorship, with 26% of survivors experiencing clinically significant fatigue symptoms at baseline (on average 18 years from diagnosis) and 29% at follow-up (on average 29 years after diagnosis). Fatigue in this study is similarly prevalent as reported by systematic reviews in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancers [1, 12], and slightly more prevalent than what a previous study in a smaller cohort of survivors in Switzerland found [3]. Of note, being fatigued may be a barrier to survey participation [33], which may result in an underestimation of fatigue prevalence both in survivors and the general population.

Our results show that in a population-based cohort of survivors, fatigue in long-term survivorship (median 18 years after diagnosis) is comparable to fatigue in the general population. This is in contrast to our previous systematic review, where we found that survivors had higher fatigue prevalence and fatigue levels than comparisons [1]. One possible explanation is that we compared survivors to a representative group of the general population rather than to healthy controls. Fatigue is common in the general population [34], where some individuals may have chronic health conditions [35], and previous studies have shown

TABLE 1 | Characteristics of the study population.

	Survivors		General population
	Baseline	Follow-Up ^a	Total N (%)
	Total N (%)	Total N (%)	Total N (%)
	1846 (100.0)	684 (100.0)	863 (100.0)
Sex			
Male	961 (52.1)	358 (52.3)	360 (41.7)
Female	885 (47.9)	326 (47.7)	503 (58.3)
Age at study (years)			
Median (IQR; range)	26.8 (9.90; 20–59)	36.7 (9.54; 25–58)	43.7 (16.88; 20–59)
20–29 years	1204 (65.2)	91 (13.3)	139 (16.1)
30–39 years	472 (25.6)	367 (53.6)	212 (24.6)
40–49 years	148 (8.0)	198 (29.0)	256 (29.7)
50–59 years	22 (1.2)	28 (4.1)	256 (29.7)
Time from baseline (years)			
Median (IQR; range)	n.a.	8.9 (4.12; 3–10)	n.a.
Time since diagnosis (years)			
Median (IQR; range)	18.0 (12.48; 5–42)	28.8 (10.44; 9–42)	n.a.
Language region			
German	1279 (69.3)	479 (70.0)	633 (73.3)
French	497 (26.9)	188 (27.5)	181 (21.0)
Italian	56 (3.0)	17 (2.5)	49 (5.7)
Missing	14 (0.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Migration background			
No	1434 (77.7)	568 (83.1)	657 (76.1)
Yes	319 (17.3)	87 (12.7)	206 (23.9)
Missing	93 (5.0)	29 (4.2)	0 (0.0)
Civil status			
Single	1393 (75.5)	504 (73.7)	309 (35.8)
Married	381 (20.6)	152 (22.2)	406 (47.0)
Divorced/Widowed	49 (2.7)	22 (3.2)	108 (12.5)
Missing	23 (1.2)	6 (0.9)	40 (4.6)
Educational achievement			
Compulsory school	217 (11.8)	67 (9.8)	49 (5.7)
Vocational training	1051 (56.9)	414 (60.5)	376 (43.6)
Upper secondary education	353 (19.1)	134 (19.6)	227 (26.3)
University education	189 (10.2)	61 (8.9)	167 (19.4)
Missing	36 (2.0)	8 (1.2)	44 (5.1)
Employment status			
Employed	1411 (76.4)	538 (78.7)	732 (84.8)
Unemployed	142 (7.7)	49 (7.2)	82 (9.5)
In education	233 (12.6)	77 (11.3)	28 (3.2)
Missing	60 (3.3)	20 (2.9)	21 (2.4)
Fatigue prevalence			
No	1365 (73.9)	486 (71.1)	638 (73.9)
Yes	481 (26.1)	198 (28.9)	225 (26.1)

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

	Survivors		General population
	Baseline	Follow-Up ^a	Total N (%)
	Total N (%)	Total N (%)	Total N (%)
	1846 (100.0)	684 (100.0)	863 (100.0)
Fatigue severity			
Mean (SD; range)	50.2 (10.81; 13–71)	49.0 (10.9; 13–71)	49.3 (10.17; 13–71)
BMI			
Mean (SD; range)	23.7 (4.7; 13–68)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	36 (2.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Vigorous-intensity physical activity (30 min/week)			
Median (IQR; range)	4 ^c (7; 0–210)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	328 (17.8)	n.a.	n.a.
Moderate-intensity physical activity (30 min/week)			
Median (IQR; range)	4 ^c (6; 0–224)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	315 (17.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Health status			
Good–Excellent	1754 (95.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Fair–Poor	92 (5.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Pain			
None–Mild	1669 (90.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Moderate–Very severe	175 (9.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	2 (0.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Late effects			
Number of organ systems affected: ^b Median (IQR)	1 (2; 0–9)	n.a.	n.a.
No	546 (29.6)	n.a.	n.a.
Any	1295 (70.2)	n.a.	n.a.
Neurological	617 (33.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Musculoskeletal	407 (22.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Cardiovascular	176 (9.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Vision	246 (13.3)	n.a.	n.a.
Hearing	207 (11.2)	n.a.	n.a.
Endocrine	248 (13.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Pulmonary	519 (28.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Digestive	266 (14.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Urinary	64 (3.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	5 (0.3)	n.a.	n.a.
Psychological distress^d			
No	1566 (84.8)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	248 (13.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	32 (1.7)	n.a.	n.a.
Diagnosis			
Leukaemia	493 (26.7)	189 (27.6)	n.a.
Lymphoma	459 (24.9)	167 (24.4)	n.a.
CNS tumour	276 (14.9)	73 (10.7)	n.a.
Other tumour	618 (33.5)	255 (27.3)	n.a.

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

	Survivors		General population
	Baseline Total N (%) 1846 (100.0)	Follow-Up ^a Total N (%) 684 (100.0)	Total N (%) 863 (100.0)
Surgery			
No	529 (28.7)	200 (29.2)	n.a.
Yes	1229 (66.6)	448 (65.5)	n.a.
Missing	88 (4.8)	36 (5.3)	n.a.
Chemotherapy			
No	376 (20.4)	117 (17.1)	n.a.
Yes	1372 (74.3)	526 (76.9)	n.a.
Missing	98 (5.3)	41 (6.0)	n.a.
Radiotherapy			
No	1092 (59.2)	386 (56.4)	n.a.
Yes	641 (34.7)	254 (37.1)	n.a.
Missing	113 (6.1)	44 (6.4)	n.a.
Stem cell transplantation			
No	1652 (89.5)	613 (89.6)	n.a.
Yes	59 (3.2)	15 (2.2)	n.a.
Missing	135 (7.3)	56 (8.2)	n.a.
Relapse/SMN			
No	1492 (80.8)	557 (81.4)	n.a.
Yes	354 (19.2)	127 (18.6)	n.a.
Age at diagnosis (years)			
Median (IQR; range)	12 (9; 0–20)	10 (9; 0–20)	n.a.
Year of diagnosis			
1976–1985	453 (24.5)	228 (33.3)	n.a.
1986–1995	687 (37.2)	299 (43.7)	n.a.
1996–2005	413 (22.4)	149 (21.8)	n.a.
2006–2015	293 (15.9)	8 (1.2)	n.a.

Note: 'Missing' is only displayed if there are missing values for the respective variable. Standardised *fatigue severity* scores range from 0 to 100, with lower scores indicating greater fatigue. *Fatigue prevalence* and *fatigue severity* stratified by participants' characteristics are presented in Tables S5 and S6.

Abbreviations: BSI-18, Brief Symptom Inventory-18; CNS, central nervous system; n.a., not available; SD, standard deviation; SMN, second malignant neoplasm.

^aAll variables (except age at study, time from baseline, time since diagnosis and fatigue) were measured at baseline.

^bNumber of organ systems affected by late effects (in neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive or urinary).

^cThe unit is '30 min/week'. A score of 4 means: 4 × 30 min of physical activity per week = 2 h of physical activity per week

^dT-score ≥ 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI)-18.

that fatigue is prevalent not only among cancer survivors, but also in persons with other chronic diseases [36]. Another reason may be a response shift, which has been shown to occur in cancer patients [37]. It is possible that survivors subconsciously compare their current fatigue to previously experienced more severe fatigue, for example, during treatment, and thus underreport symptoms of fatigue.

Regarding longitudinal patterns of fatigue, our results are in line with studies in patients closer to diagnosis and treatment, showing that fatigue at baseline predicts fatigue at follow-up [11,

16, 33]. In our study, the majority of survivors either experienced *no/low fatigue* or *persistent fatigue*, and only a minority changed their fatigue status. Similarly, a study from the United States found that fatigue in Hodgkin lymphoma survivors did not change significantly from the end of therapy to 36 months post-therapy [15]. Another study found a larger proportion of survivors with *persistent fatigue* (31%) or *improving fatigue* (21%), and a smaller proportion of survivors with *no/low fatigue* (39%) [16]. These differences may be due to the assessment used (Fatigue Questionnaire vs. SF-36 vitality scale in our study) and different lengths of follow-up periods (median 2.7 vs. 8.9 years in our

TABLE 2 | Characteristics associated with *persistent fatigue* in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer (from multivariable logistic regression).

	Persistent fatigue (Ref. no/low fatigue)			
	<i>n</i>	OR ^a	95% CI	<i>p</i> -value
Total	433			
Diagnosis				
Leukaemia		Ref.		
Lymphoma	0.11	0.01	1.18	0.068
CNS tumour	0.51	0.04	6.25	0.602
Other tumour	0.12	0.01	1.27	0.078
Treatment				
Surgery (Ref. No)	4.44	0.44	44.61	0.205
Chemotherapy (Ref. No)	1.36	0.47	3.95	0.577
Radiotherapy (Ref. No)	1.28	0.63	2.60	0.487
SCT (Ref. No)	n.a. ^b			
Relapse/SMN: Yes (Ref. No)	0.42	0.17	1.04	0.060
Age at diagnosis [continuous]	1.01	0.88	1.15	0.933
Year of diagnosis				
1976–1985	Ref.			
1986–1995	1.02	0.30	3.44	0.976
1996–2015	1.58	0.17	14.55	0.687
Health status: Fair–Poor (Ref. Good–Excellent)	n.a. ^d			
Late effects: Number of organ systems affected^c	1.49	1.19	1.87	0.001
Psychological distress:^d Yes (Ref. No)	14.53	5.94	35.57	<0.001
Pain: Moderate–Very severe (Ref. None–Mild)	6.05	2.05	17.87	0.001
BMI [continuous]	1.04	0.96	1.11	0.349
Moderate-intensity physical activity (30 min/week)	0.95	0.90	1.00	0.038
Year of study participation (year)	1.08	0.90	1.31	0.416
Age at study: (years)	1.06	0.94	1.19	0.365
Sex: Female (Ref. Male)	1.06	0.52	2.13	0.876
Civil status				
Single/Divorced/Widowed	Ref.			
Married	0.59	0.25	1.41	0.237
Educational achievement				
Compulsory school	2.04	0.64	6.53	0.231
Vocational training	Ref.			
Upper secondary education	1.39	0.61	3.14	0.432
University education	1.17	0.38	3.60	0.786
Employment situation				
Employed	Ref.			
Unemployed	0.62	0.15	2.59	0.509
In education	1.83	0.68	4.93	0.229

Note: Models adjusted for all variables displayed in the table. Explanatory variables were measured at baseline. Bold font indicates results with *p*-values less than 0.05. Time since diagnosis, vigorous-intensity physical activity, and the organ-specific late effects variables were excluded from this analysis due to collinearity with other variables.

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; CI, confidence interval, CNS, central nervous system; OR, odds ratio; SMN, second malignant neoplasm.

^aHigher odds ratio indicates a higher likelihood to be in the ‘persistent fatigue’ group as compared to the ‘no/low fatigue’ group.

^bToo few observations (*n* < 25 in one category), variable excluded from model.

^cNumber of organ systems affected by late effects (range: 0–9; neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive or urinary).

^d*T*-score ≥ 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI)-18.

study). LeBlanc and colleagues in the United States also used the SF-36 vitality scale to measure fatigue in adult survivors of non-Hodgkin lymphoma and found very similar results to ours, although survivors were significantly older (mean age 62 years) [33].

It is unclear why fatigue persists in survivors of childhood cancers. First, it may be difficult to treat fatigue symptoms. However, there is enough evidence of interventions that improve fatigue symptoms [38]. Thus, treatment resistance should not be a major concern. Other theories point to methodological problems, as the SF-36 is assessed retrospectively for 4 weeks, and the follow-up time in our study was, on average, 9 years. Specifically, fatigue status may have changed several times over the unobserved period. Finally, it is possible that survivors did not receive adequate treatment, as evidence suggests that there are several communication barriers between healthcare practitioners and survivors for discussing fatigue in appointments [4, 39].

With current practice, fatigue symptoms improve only for a small proportion of fatigued survivors. It is therefore recommended to strengthen current practice by implementing a more consistent screening and treatment approach: healthcare professionals responsible for the follow-up care of survivors of childhood cancer are encouraged to utilise published clinical practice guidelines for the surveillance and treatment of fatigue [1, 4, 38]. Simple, low-threshold interventions such as providing survivors with an information booklet can help to raise awareness and encourage survivors to take action or seek help [40]. In Switzerland, such information booklets are provided by the Swiss Cancer League and are available for free online (www.krebsliga.ch). In addition, capacity building in paediatric oncology rehabilitation with healthcare professionals who can provide effective interventions for fatigue (occupational therapists, physiotherapists, exercise therapists and psychotherapists), as well as strengthening the collaboration between paediatric oncologists and paediatric oncology rehabilitation professionals, could help to provide adequate care for survivors.

Persistent fatigue was associated with clinical characteristics: more organ systems affected by late effects, psychological distress, pain, and less time spent on moderate-intensity physical activity. In line with this, a study from Belgium found that psychological symptoms predicted fatigue 1 year later [41], and a study in adult non-Hodgkin lymphoma survivors found post-traumatic stress symptoms and a higher number of comorbidities to be associated with persistent fatigue [33]. We found that more time spent in moderate-intensity physical activity was associated with a lower likelihood of *persistent fatigue*, consistent with the Physical Activity in Childhood Cancer Survivors (PACCS) study, which reported that light physical activity was associated with improvement in fatigue in survivors [42]. Examples of moderate-intensity or light physical activity are walking briskly, cycling with low effort, or water aerobics. However, the relationship between fatigue and physical activity is likely complex: A study from the Netherlands showed that fatigue is a causal factor for decreased physical activity [43]. On the other hand, evidence from intervention studies shows that physical activity interventions are effective in reducing fatigue symptoms [38]. Thus, the relationship is likely bidirectional.

Overall, our study confirms that it is primarily factors that are at least partly modifiable, such as health problems, psychological distress, pain and physical inactivity, that contribute to fatigue in long-term survivorship. The few studies available on childhood cancer survivors suggest that targeting modifiable factors, for example, physical activity [44] or psychological distress [45], may reduce fatigue symptoms. These factors, and additional contributors like poor sleep [3], can be targeted with interventions [1, 4, 38]. Our study adds evidence that these factors are associated with longitudinal fatigue patterns in survivorship.

The major strength of our study is its nationwide and population-based design. Other strengths are the good response rate of the SCCSS, which is comparable to other survivor cohorts [46–48], and the availability of general population data. A limitation of our study is the use of a generic fatigue measure (SF-36) instead of a cancer-specific and/or multidimensional measure. However, generic measures may be used to allow for comparison with other groups [49]. Also, the SF-36 assesses symptoms over a 4-week period. It is possible that the fatigue status of survivors changed over the unobserved period. It is not predictable in which direction this may bias our results. In addition, the variability in the timing of follow-up assessments may have influenced placement of participants into fatigue patterns, and future studies with uniform assessment intervals may clarify these patterns. Attrition bias may be an issue, as not all baseline participants participated in follow-up. Another limitation is that survivors are prone to response bias when completing quality-of-life surveys [50]. This may cause an underestimation of the prevalence and severity of fatigue. Finally, the response rate in the general population was relatively low, which may have further biased our results.

In conclusion, our study provides data on longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors and identifies factors associated with the different patterns. Although fatigue prevalence and severity of survivors were comparable to the general population, fatigue is a considerable problem for long-term survivors, with a quarter of survivors experiencing fatigue symptoms. Almost two-thirds of survivors (64%) had consistently low or no fatigue at both timepoints, but 15% of survivors were persistently fatigued. It is recommended to strengthen current clinical practice by implementing surveillance and treatment guidelines for fatigue. Managing late effects, pain and psychological distress, and promoting physical activity can help to improve fatigue symptoms and quality of life of survivors.

Author Contributions

Salome Christen: conceptualisation (equal), formal analysis (equal), funding acquisition (equal), methodology (equal), project administration (equal), software (equal), validation (equal), visualisation (lead), writing – original draft (lead), writing – review and editing (lead). **Luzius Mader:** conceptualisation (equal), methodology (equal), supervision (equal), data curation (equal), investigation (equal), supervision (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **André O. von Bueren:** resources (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Eva Maria Tinner:** resources (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Grit Sommer:** data curation (equal), investigation (equal), resources (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Christina Schindera:** resources (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Claudia Kuehni:** conceptualisation

(equal), data curation (equal), funding acquisition (equal), investigation (equal), methodology (equal), resources (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Katharina Roser:** conceptualisation (equal), methodology (equal), supervision (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal). **Gisela Michel:** conceptualisation (equal), funding acquisition (equal), investigation (equal), methodology (equal), resources (equal), supervision (equal), validation (equal), writing – review and editing (equal).

Acknowledgements

We thank the study team of the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study (Nicolas von der Weid, Fabiën Belle, Philippa Jörgler, Corinne Matti, Carina Nigg, Maša Zarkovic) and the data managers of the Swiss Paediatric Oncology Group. We also thank the Childhood Cancer Registry of the Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine (ISPM) at the University of Bern for the data provided in March 2022.

Open access publishing facilitated by Universität Luzern, as part of the Wiley - Universität Luzern agreement via the Consortium Of Swiss Academic Libraries.

Ethics Statement

This study involving human participants is compliant with the Swiss Human Research Act (810.30 Federal Act of 30 September 2011 on Research involving Human Beings) and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments. Specifically, ethical approval for the SCCSS was granted by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Bern (KEK-Nr. 166/14 and 2021-01462). Ethics approval for the Swiss general population data collection was granted by the Ethikkommission Nordwest- und Zentralschweiz (EKNZ 2015–075).

Consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the information in this manuscript were accessed on secure servers of the Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine at the University of Bern. Individual-level, fully anonymised, sensitive data can only be made available for researchers who fulfil the respective legal requirements. Requests for data from the Childhood Cancer Registry must be directed to the Childhood Cancer Registry of Switzerland (<https://www.childhoodcancerregistry.ch/>). Requests for data from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study (SCCSS; <https://www.swiss-ccss.ch/>) should be communicated to the study lead, Claudia E. Kuehni (claudia.kuehni@unibe.ch).

References

1. S. Christen, K. Roser, R. L. Mulder, et al., “Recommendations for the Surveillance of Cancer-Related Fatigue in Childhood, Adolescent, and Young Adult Cancer Survivors: A Report From the International Late Effects of Childhood Cancer Guideline Harmonization Group,” *Journal of Cancer Survivorship: Research and Practice* 14 (2020): 923–938, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11764-020-00904-9>.
2. A. Penson, I. Walraven, E. Bronkhorst, et al., “The Impact of Cancer-Related Fatigue on HRQOL in Survivors of Childhood Cancer: A DCCSS LATER Study,” *Cancers* 14 (2022): 2851, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14122851>.
3. T. Sláma, F. N. Belle, S. Strebler, et al., “Prevalence and Factors Associated With Cancer-Related Fatigue in Swiss Adult Survivors of

Childhood Cancer,” *Journal of Cancer Survivorship: Research and Practice* 18, no. 1 (2024): 135–143, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11764-023-01413-1>.

4. C. Jankowski, K. M. Carpenter, O. Aranha, et al., “Cancer-Related Fatigue: NCCN Clinical Practice Guidelines in Oncology. Version 2.2023,” NCCN, 2023.
5. M. Karimi, A. D. Cox, S. V. White, and C. W. Karlson, “Fatigue, Physical and Functional Mobility, and Obesity in Pediatric Cancer Survivors,” *Cancer Nursing* 201943, no. 4: E239–E245, <https://doi.org/10.1097/NCC.0000000000000712>.
6. S. A. Eikeland, K. B. Smeland, V. C. Simensen, et al., “Chronic Fatigue in Long-Term Survivors of Hodgkin’s Lymphoma After Contemporary Risk-Adapted Treatment,” *Acta Oncologica* 62 (2023): 80–88, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0284186X.2023.2168215>.
7. A. Fabi, R. Bhargava, S. Fatigoni, et al., “Cancer-Related Fatigue: ,” *Annals of Oncology* 31 (2020): 713–723, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annonc.2020.02.016>.
8. M. C. Hooke and L. A. Linder, “Symptoms in Children Receiving Treatment for Cancer—Part I: Fatigue, Sleep Disturbance, and Nausea/Vomiting,” *Journal of Pediatric Oncology Nursing* 36 (2019): 244–261, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043454219849576>.
9. E. Nowe, Y. Stöbel-Richter, A. Sender, K. Leuteritz, M. Friedrich, and K. Geue, “Cancer-Related Fatigue in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Systematic Review of the Literature,” *Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology* 118 (2017): 63–69, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.critrevonc.2017.08.004>.
10. S. S. Jacobs, J. S. Withycombe, S. M. Castellino, et al., “Longitudinal Use of Patient Reported Outcomes in Pediatric Leukemia and Lymphoma Reveals Clinically Relevant Symptomatic Adverse Events,” *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 69 (2022): e29986, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.29986>.
11. E. Irestorm, L. M. H. Steur, G. J. L. Kaspers, et al., “Fatigue Trajectories During Pediatric ALL Therapy Are Associated With Fatigue After Treatment: A National Longitudinal Cohort Study,” *Supportive Care in Cancer* 31 (2022): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-022-07456-x>.
12. S. van Deuren, A. Boonstra, E. van Dulmen-den Broeder, N. Blijlevens, H. Knoop, and J. Loonen, “Severe Fatigue After Treatment for Childhood Cancer,” *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 3, no. 3 (2020): CD012681, <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012681.pub2>.
13. E. M. van Dijk-Lokkart, L. M. H. Steur, K. I. Braam, et al., “Longitudinal Development of Cancer-Related Fatigue and Physical Activity in Childhood Cancer Patients,” *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 66 (2019): e27949, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.27949>.
14. S. Walsh, M. Mulraney, M. C. McCarthy, and L. C. R. de, “Fatigue in Children Who Have Recently Completed Treatment for Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia: A Longitudinal Study,” *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes* 22 (2024): 27, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-024-02241-2>.
15. C. F. Macpherson, M. C. Hooke, D. L. Friedman, et al., “Exercise and Fatigue in Adolescent and Young Adult Survivors of Hodgkin Lymphoma: A Report From the Children’s Oncology Group,” *Journal of Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology* 4 (2015): 137–140, <https://doi.org/10.1089/jayao.2015.0013>.
16. B. Zeller, J. H. Loge, A. Kanellopoulos, H. Hamre, V. B. Wyller, and E. Ruud, “Chronic Fatigue in Long-Term Survivors of Childhood Lymphomas and Leukemia: Persistence and Associated Clinical Factors,” *Journal of Pediatric Hematology/Oncology* 36 (2014): 438–444, <https://doi.org/10.1097/mpb.0000000000000051>.
17. E. Irestorm, A. Y. N. Schouten-van Meeteren, M. van Gorp, et al., “The Development of Fatigue After Treatment for Pediatric Brain Tumors Does Not Differ Between Tumor Locations,” *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 71, no. 7 (2024): e31028, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.31028>.
18. C. E. Kuehni, C. S. Rueegg, G. Michel, et al., “Cohort Profile: The Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study,” *International Journal of Epidemiology* 41 (2012): 1553–1564, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyrl42>.

19. G. Michel, W. N. von der Weid, M. Zwahlen, et al., "The Swiss Childhood Cancer Registry: Rationale, Organisation and Results for the Years 2001–2005," *Swiss Medical Weekly* 137 (2007): 502–509.
20. G. Michel, J. Baenziger, J. Brodbeck, L. Mader, C. E. Kuehni, and K. Roser, "The Brief Symptom Inventory in the Swiss General Population: Presentation of Norm Scores and Predictors of Psychological Distress," *PLoS One* 19 (2024): e0305192, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0305192>.
21. K. Roser, L. Mader, J. Baenziger, G. Sommer, C. E. Kuehni, and G. Michel, "Health-Related Quality of Life in Switzerland: Normative Data for the SF-36v2 Questionnaire," *Quality of Life Research* 28 (2019): 1963–1977, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-019-02161-5>.
22. J. E. Ware and B. Gandek, "Overview of the SF-36 Health Survey and the International Quality of Life Assessment (IQOLA) Project," *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 51 (1998): 903–912, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-4356\(98\)00081-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-4356(98)00081-X).
23. L. F. Brown, K. Kroenke, D. E. Theobald, and J. Wu, "Comparison of SF-36 Vitality Scale and Fatigue Symptom Inventory in Assessing Cancer-Related Fatigue," *Supportive Care in Cancer* 19 (2011): 1255–1259, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-011-1148-2>.
24. R. C. Reulen, M. P. Zeegers, C. Jenkinson, et al., "The Use of the SF-36 Questionnaire in Adult Survivors of Childhood Cancer: Evaluation of Data Quality, Score Reliability, and Scaling Assumptions," *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes* 4 (2006): 77, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7525-4-77>.
25. M. Morfeld, I. Kirchberger, and M. Bullinger, *SF-36 Fragebogen zum Gesundheitszustand: Deutsche Version des Short Form-36 Health Survey*, 2nd ed. (Hogrefe, 2011).
26. K. A. Donovan, P. B. Jacobsen, B. J. Small, P. N. Munster, and M. A. Andrykowski, "Identifying Clinically Meaningful Fatigue With the Fatigue Symptom Inventory," *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management* 36 (2008): 480–487, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpainsymman.2007.11.013>.
27. E. Steliarova-Foucher, C. Stiller, B. Lacour, and P. Kaatsch, "International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition," *Cancer* 103 (2005): 1457–1467, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.20910>.
28. G. H. Franke, S. Jaeger, H. Glaesmer, C. Barkmann, K. Petrowski, and E. Braehler, "Psychometric Analysis of the Brief Symptom Inventory 18 (BSI-18) in a Representative German Sample," *BMC Medical Research Methodology* 17 (2017): 14, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-016-0283-3>.
29. L. R. Derogatis, "BSI 18: Brief Symptom Inventory 18," in *Administration, Scoring, and Procedures Manual* (NCS Pearson, 2000).
30. A. Levesque, M. Caru, M. Duval, C. Laverdière, S. Marjerrison, and S. Sultan, "Cancer-Related Fatigue in Childhood Cancer Survivors: A Systematic Scoping Review on Contributors of Fatigue and How They Are Targeted by Non-Pharmacological Interventions," *Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology* 179 (2022): 103804, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.critrevonc.2022.103804>.
31. V. A. Sanchez, M. M. Shuey, P. C. Dinh, et al., "Patient-Reported Functional Impairment due to Hearing Loss and Tinnitus After Cisplatin-Based Chemotherapy," *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 41, no. 12 (2023): 2211–2226, <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.22.01456>.
32. I. Vaz-Luis, A. Di Meglio, J. Havas, et al., "Long-Term Longitudinal Patterns of Patient-Reported Fatigue after Breast Cancer: A Group-Based Trajectory Analysis," *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 40 (2022): 2148–2162, <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.21.01958>.
33. M. R. LeBlanc, S. Zimmerman, T. W. LeBlanc, A. L. Bryant, K. E. Hudson, and S. K. Smith, "Persistent Fatigue Among Long-Term Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma Survivors," *Leukemia & Lymphoma* 63 (2022): 344–352, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10428194.2021.1984450>.
34. C. Galland-Decker, P. Marques-Vidal, and P. Vollenweider, "Prevalence and Factors Associated With Fatigue in the Lausanne Middle-Aged Population: A Population-Based, Cross-Sectional Survey," *BMJ Open* 9 (2019): e027070, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-027070>.
35. Federal Office of Public Health, "The Majority of the Swiss Population is Satisfied With Healthcare," FOPH, 2024, <https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/en/home/das-bag/aktuell/medienmitteilungen.msg-id-99203.html>.
36. Y. M. J. Goërtz, A. M. J. Braamse, M. A. Spruit, et al., "Fatigue in Patients With Chronic Disease: Results From the Population-Based Lifelines Cohort Study," *Scientific Reports* 11 (2021): 20977, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-00337-z>.
37. M. R. Visser, E. M. Smets, M. A. Sprangers, and H. J. de Haes, "How Response Shift May Affect the Measurement of Change in Fatigue," *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management* 20 (2000): 12–18, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924\(00\)00148-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924(00)00148-2).
38. P. D. Robinson, S. Oberoi, D. Tomlinson, et al., "Management of Fatigue in Children and Adolescents With Cancer and in Paediatric Recipients of Haemopoietic Stem-Cell Transplants: A Clinical Practice Guideline," *Lancet Child & Adolescent Health* 2 (2018): 371–378, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(18\)30059-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(18)30059-2).
39. M. Milzer, A. S. Wagner, M. E. Schmidt, et al., "Patient-physician Communication About Cancer-Related Fatigue: A Survey of Patient-perceived Barriers," *Journal of Cancer Research and Clinical Oncology* 150 (2024): 29, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00432-023-05555-8>.
40. M. E. Schmidt, M. Milzer, C. Weiß, P. Reinke, M. Grapp, and K. Steindorf, "Cancer-Related Fatigue: Benefits of Information Booklets to Improve Patients' knowledge and Empowerment," *Supportive Care in Cancer* 30 (2022): 4813–4821, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-022-06833-w>.
41. D. Vanrusselt, C. Sleurs, S. Prikken, et al., "Associations Between Cancer-Related Distress and Fatigue in Childhood Cancer Survivors: A Longitudinal Study," *Psycho-Oncology* 32, no. 3 (2023): 393–400, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pon.6084>.
42. M. Bratteteig, M. Grydeland, S. A. Anderssen, et al., "A Physical Activity in Childhood Cancer Survivors (PACCS) Study: Poster Presentation," Lucerne, Switzerland; June 29, 2024.
43. A. Penson, I. G. Bucur, I. Walraven, M. A. Grootenhuis, H. Maurice-Stam, and M. van der Heiden-van der Loo, "Structural Equation Modeling to Explore Putative Causal Factors for Chronic Fatigue in Childhood Cancer Survivors: A DCCSS LATER Study," *Journal of Cancer Survivorship: Research and Practice* (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11764-024-01738-5>.
44. L. Moberg, J. Fritch, D. Westmark, et al., "Effect of Physical Activity on Fatigue in Childhood Cancer Survivors: A Systematic Review," *Supportive Care in Cancer* 30 (2022): 6441–6449, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-022-06960-4>.
45. A. Boonstra, M. Gielissen, E. van Dulmen-den Broeder, N. Blijlevens, H. Knoop, and J. Loonen, "Cognitive Behavior Therapy for Persistent Severe Fatigue in Childhood Cancer Survivors: A Pilot Study," *Journal of Pediatric Hematology/Oncology* 41, no. 4 (2019): 313–318, <https://doi.org/10.1097/MPH.0000000000001345>.
46. M. M. Hawkins, E. R. Lancashire, D. L. Winter, et al., "The British Childhood Cancer Survivor Study: Objectives, Methods, Population Structure, Response Rates and Initial Descriptive Information," *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 50 (2008): 1018–1025, <https://doi.org/10.1002/psc.21335>.
47. I. C. Huang, T. M. Brinkman, K. Kenzik, et al., "Association Between the Prevalence of Symptoms and Health-Related Quality of Life in Adult Survivors of Childhood Cancer: A Report From the St Jude Lifetime Cohort Study," *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 31 (2013): 4242–4251, <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2012.47.8867>.
48. L. L. Robison, G. T. Armstrong, J. D. Boice, et al., "The Childhood Cancer Survivor Study: A National Cancer Institute-Supported Resource for Outcome and Intervention Research," *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 27 (2009): 2308–2318, <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2009.22.3339>.
49. J. Weis and M. Horneber, *Cancer-Related Fatigue*, 1st ed. (Springer Healthcare Communications, 2015).
50. T. E. O'Leary, L. Diller, and C. J. Recklitis, "The Effects of Response Bias on Self-Reported Quality of Life Among Childhood Cancer Survivors," *Quality of Life Research* 16 (2007): 1211–1220, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-007-9231-3>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Table S1: Fatigue prevalence (SF-36 vitality scale score ≤ 45) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at baseline as compared to the general population ($N = 2490$; from multivariable logistic regression). **Table**

S2: Fatigue prevalence (SF-36 vitality scale score ≤ 45) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at follow-up as compared to the general population ($N = 1447$; from multivariable logistic regression). **Table S3:**

Fatigue severity (SF-36 vitality scale score) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at baseline as compared to the Swiss general population ($N = 2490$; from multivariable linear regression). **Table S4:**

Fatigue severity (SF-36 vitality scale score) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at follow-up as compared to the Swiss general population ($N = 1447$; from multivariable linear regression). **Table**

S5: Fatigue prevalence (SF-36 vitality scale score ≤ 45) stratified by the characteristics of the study population. **Table S6:** Fatigue severity (SF-36 vitality scale score) stratified by the characteristics of the study population.

Table S7: Frequency of specific longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer, and corresponding fatigue severity (SF-36 vitality scale score), and fatigue prevalence and severity in the general population. **Table S8:** Baseline characteristics associated with persistent fatigue (from univariable logistic regression). **Appendix 1:**

Detailed information on coding and scoring of explanatory variables from the SCCSS and the general population.

Longitudinal patterns of fatigue in long-term survivors of childhood and adolescent cancers: A report from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study.

Salome Christen, MA¹; Luzius Mader, PhD²; André O. von Bueren, MD PhD,^{3,4}; Eva Maria Tinner^{5,6}; Grit Sommer, PhD⁷; Christina Schindera^{7,8}; Claudia E. Kuehni, MD^{5,7}; Katharina Roser, PhD¹; Gisela Michel, PhD¹.

¹Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland; salome.christen@unilu.ch; katharina.rosler@unilu.ch; gisela.michel@unilu.ch

²Cancer Registry Bern Solothurn, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland; luzius.mader@unibe.ch

³Department of Pediatrics, Gynecology and Obstetrics, Division of General Pediatrics, Pediatric Hematology and Oncology Unit, University Hospitals of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland. andre.vonburen@hug.ch

⁴Department of Pediatrics, Gynecology and Obstetrics, CANSEARCH Research Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine, University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland. andre.vonburen@hug.ch

⁵Division of Pediatric Hematology/ Oncology, Department of Pediatrics, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland; eva.tinner@insel.ch,

⁶University Institute of Internal Medicine, Cantonal Hospital Baselland, Liestal, Switzerland, eva-maria.tinner@ksbl.ch

⁷Childhood Cancer Research Group, Institute of Social and Preventive Medicine, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland; gritti.sommer@unibe.ch , christina.schindera@unibe.ch , claudia.kuehni@unibe.ch

⁸Division of Paediatric Oncology/Haematology, University Children's Hospital Basel, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland; christina.schindera@unibe.ch

Corresponding author: Gisela Michel, Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine, University of Lucerne, Lucerne, Switzerland; Email: gisela.michel@unilu.ch

Supplemental Table S1. *Fatigue prevalence* (SF-36 vitality scale score \leq 45) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at baseline as compared to the general population (N=2490; from multivariable logistic regression).

Fatigue prevalence	OR	95%CI		p-value
Population				
General population	Ref.			
Survivors at baseline	0.93	0.73	1.19	0.546
Sex				
Male	Ref.			
Female	1.68	1.39	2.03	<0.001
Age				
20-29 years	Ref.			
30-39 years	1.09	0.84	1.41	0.527
40-49 years	1.15	0.81	1.63	0.432
50-59 years	0.92	0.60	1.42	0.714
Language region				
German	Ref.			
French	1.84	1.50	2.26	<0.001
Italian	1.17	0.73	1.88	0.519
Migration background				
No migration background	Ref.			
Migration background	1.33	1.06	1.67	0.013
Civil status				
Single	Ref.			
Married	0.80	0.62	1.04	0.096
Divorced/Widowed	0.92	0.59	1.43	0.711
Educational achievement				
Compulsory school	1.82	1.34	2.45	<0.001
Vocational training	Ref.			
Upper secondary education	1.11	0.87	1.42	0.383
University education	1.13	0.85	1.50	0.404
Employment situation				
Employed	Ref.			
Unemployed	1.86	1.36	2.54	<0.001
In education	1.20	0.87	1.65	0.260

Note: Results from multivariable logistic regression with *fatigue prevalence* (SF-36 vitality scale score \leq 45) as the dependent variable, adjusted for all variables displayed in the table (population, sex, age, language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement, and employment situation). Bold font indicates results with p-values <0.05 . Abbreviations: CI=confidence interval, OR=odds ratio.

Supplemental Table S2. *Fatigue prevalence* (SF-36 vitality scale score \leq 45) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at follow-up as compared to the general population (N=1447; from multivariable logistic regression).

Fatigue prevalence	OR	95%CI		p-value
Population				
General population	Ref.			
Survivors at follow-up	0.98	0.74	1.32	0.916
Sex				
Male	Ref.			
Female	1.82	1.42	2.35	<0.001
Age				
20-29 years	Ref.			
30-39 years	1.04	0.70	1.54	0.836
40-49 years	0.96	0.62	1.50	0.869
50-59 years	0.80	0.49	1.31	0.380
Language region				
German	Ref.			
French	2.19	1.66	2.88	<0.001
Italian	0.64	0.32	1.32	0.230
Migration background				
No migration background	Ref.			
Migration background	1.16	0.85	1.58	0.355
Civil status				
Single	Ref.			
Married	0.83	0.61	1.14	0.254
Divorced/Widowed	0.87	0.53	1.45	0.597
Educational achievement				
Compulsory school	1.91	1.23	2.97	0.004
Vocational training	Ref.			
Upper secondary education	1.12	0.82	1.52	0.475
University education	1.04	0.72	1.51	0.819
Employment situation				
Employed	Ref.			
Unemployed	2.18	1.45	3.25	<0.001
In education	1.05	0.64	1.72	0.849

Note: Results from multivariable logistic regression with *fatigue prevalence* (SF-36 vitality scale score \leq 45) as the dependent variable, adjusted for all variables displayed in the table (population, sex, age, language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement, and employment situation). Bold font indicates results with p-values <0.05 . Abbreviations: CI=confidence interval, OR=odds ratio.

Supplemental Table S3. *Fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at baseline as compared to the Swiss general population (N=2490; from multivariable linear regression).

Fatigue severity	b	95%CI	p-value
Population			
General population	Ref.		
Survivors at baseline	1.15	0.06 2.24	0.038
Sex			
Male	Ref.		
Female	-2.84	-3.66 -2.02	<0.001
Age			
20-29 years	Ref.		
30-39 years	-0.80	-1.95 0.35	0.171
40-49 years	-0.35	-1.90 1.19	0.654
50-59 years	-1.11	-2.97 0.75	0.242
Language region			
German	Ref.		
French	-3.15	-4.10 -2.19	<0.001
Italian	-0.66	-2.76 1.44	0.539
Migration background			
No migration background	Ref.		
Migration background	-1.97	-3.01 -0.94	<0.001
Civil status			
Single	Ref.		
Married	1.46	0.33 2.58	0.011
Divorced/Widowed	1.19	-0.77 3.16	0.233
Educational achievement			
Compulsory school	-2.32	-3.76 -0.88	0.002
Vocational training	Ref.		
Upper secondary education	-0.22	-1.26 0.82	0.681
University education	-0.30	-1.56 0.97	0.646
Employment situation			
Employed	Ref.		
Unemployed	-3.45	-4.96 -1.94	<0.001
In education	-0.86	-2.29 0.57	0.238

Note: Results from multivariable linear regression with *fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score) as the dependent variable, adjusted for all variables displayed in the table (population, sex, age, language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement, and employment situation). Standardized *fatigue severity* scores range from 0 to 100, with lower scores indicating greater fatigue. Bold font indicates results with p-values <0.05. Abbreviations: *b*=unstandardized regression coefficient, CI=confidence interval.

Supplemental Table S4. *Fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score) in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer at follow-up as compared to the Swiss general population (N=1447; from multivariable linear regression).

Fatigue severity	b	95%CI		p-value
Population				
General population	Ref.			
Survivors at follow-up	0.23	-1.05	1.50	0.728
Sex				
Male	Ref.			
Female	-2.31	-3.39	-1.23	<0.001
Age				
20-29 years	Ref.			
30-39 years	0.10	-1.64	1.84	0.910
40-49 years	0.46	-1.48	2.41	0.640
50-59 years	-0.19	-2.34	1.96	0.861
Language region				
German	Ref.			
French	-3.52	-4.80	-2.24	<0.001
Italian	0.53	-2.15	3.20	0.699
Migration background				
No migration background	Ref.			
Migration background	-0.65	-2.06	0.75	0.364
Civil status				
Single	Ref.			
Married	1.38	0.01	2.74	0.049
Divorced/Widowed	1.02	-1.17	3.21	0.362
Educational achievement				
Compulsory school	-2.51	-4.60	-0.43	0.018
Vocational training	Ref.			
Upper secondary education	-0.46	-1.78	0.87	0.499
University education	-0.19	-1.79	1.40	0.814
Employment situation				
Employed	Ref.			
Unemployed	-3.87	-5.82	-1.92	<0.001
In education	0.41	-1.79	2.61	0.713

Note: Results from multivariable linear regression with *fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score) as the dependent variable, adjusted for all variables displayed in the table (population, sex, age, language region, migration background, civil status, educational achievement, and employment situation). Standardized *fatigue severity* scores range from 0 to 100, with lower scores indicating greater fatigue (fatigue severity). Bold font indicates results with p-values <0.05. Abbreviations: b=unstandardized regression coefficient, CI=confidence interval.

Supplemental Table S5. Fatigue prevalence (SF-36 vitality scale score≤45) stratified by the characteristics of the study population.

	Survivors				General population	
	Baseline		Follow-up*		Total N (% ^a)	With fatigue N (% ^b)
	Total N (% ^a)	With fatigue N (% ^b)	Total N (% ^a)	With fatigue N (% ^b)		
	1846 (100.0%)		684 (100.0%)		863 (100.0%)	
Sex						
Male	961 (52.1)	211 (22.0)	358 (52.3)	85 (23.7)	360 (41.7)	64 (17.8)
Female	885 (47.9)	270 (30.5)	326 (47.7)	113 (34.7)	503 (58.3)	161 (32.0)
Age at study [years]						
Median (IQR; range)	26.8 (9.9; 20-59)	26.7 (9.6; 20-55)	36.7 (9.5; 25-58)	37.7 (9.8; 26-58)	43.7 (16.8;20-60)	41.5 (17.2;20-60)
20-29 years	1204 (65.2)	315 (26.2)	91 (13.3)	26 (28.6)	139 (16.1)	41 (29.5)
30-39 years	472 (25.6)	113 (23.9)	367 (53.7)	104 (28.3)	212 (24.6)	60 (28.3)
40-49 years	148 (8.0)	45 (30.4)	198 (28.9)	57 (28.8)	256 (29.7)	67 (26.2)
50-59 years	22 (1.2)	8 (36.4)	28 (4.1)	11 (39.3)	256 (29.7)	57 (22.3)
Time from baseline [years]						
Median (IQR; range)	n.a.	n.a.	8.9 (4.1; 3-10)	8.8 (4.8; 4-10)	n.a.	n.a.
Time since diagnosis [years]						
Median (IQR; range)	18.0 (12.5; 5-42)	17.1 (12.6; 6-42)	28.8 (10.5; 9-42)	28.9 (10.1; 10-42)	n.a.	n.a.
Language region						
German	1279 (69.3)	281 (22.0)	479 (70.0)	116 (24.2)	633 (73.3)	145 (22.9)
French	497 (26.9)	172 (34.6)	188 (27.5)	78 (41.5)	181 (21.0)	74 (40.9)
Italian	56 (3.0)	23 (41.1)	17 (2.5)	4 (23.5)	49 (5.7)	6 (12.2)
Missing	14 (0.8)		. (.)		. (.)	
Migration background						
No	1434 (77.7)	344 (24.0)	568 (83.0)	151 (26.6)	657 (76.1)	164 (25.0)
Yes	319 (17.3)	113 (35.4)	87 (12.7)	35 (40.2)	206 (23.9)	61 (29.6)
Missing	93 (5.0)		29 (4.2)		. (.)	
Civil status						
Single	1393 (75.5)	367 (26.3)	504 (73.7)	145 (28.8)	309 (35.8)	85 (27.5)
Married	381 (20.6)	91 (23.9)	152 (22.2)	46 (30.3)	406 (47.0)	101 (24.9)
Divorced/Widowed	49 (2.7)	13 (26.5)	22 (3.2)	5 (22.7)	108 (12.5)	30 (27.8)
Missing	23 (1.2)		6 (0.9)		40 (4.6)	
Educational achievement						
Compulsory school	217 (11.8)	86 (39.6)	67 (9.8)	28 (41.8)	49 (5.7)	21 (42.9)
Vocational training	1051 (56.9)	248 (23.6)	414 (60.5)	113 (27.3)	376 (43.6)	94 (25.0)
Upper secondary education	353 (19.1)	84 (23.8)	134 (19.6)	37 (27.6)	227 (26.3)	59 (26.0)
University education	189 (10.2)	56 (29.6)	61 (8.9)	17 (27.9)	167 (19.4)	41 (24.6)
Missing	36 (2.0)		8 (1.2)		44 (5.1)	
Employment status						
Employed	1411 (76.4)	333 (23.6)	538 (78.7)	139 (25.8)	732 (84.8)	181 (24.7)
Unemployed	142 (7.7)	58 (40.8)	49 (7.2)	28 (57.1)	82 (9.5)	33 (40.2)
In education	233 (12.6)	70 (30.0)	77 (11.3)	24 (31.2)	28 (3.2)	6 (21.4)
Missing	60 (3.3)		20 (2.9)		21 (2.4)	
Fatigue prevalence						
Yes	1365 (73.9)	n.a.	486 (71.1)	n.a.	638 (73.9)	n.a.
No	481 (26.1)	n.a.	198 (28.9)	n.a.	225 (26.1)	n.a.
Fatigue severity						
Mean (SD; range)	50.2 (10.80)	36.0 (6.60)	49.0 (10.90)	35.3 (6.60)	49.3 (10.20)	35.8 (6.50)
Body Mass Index						
Mean (SD; range)	23.7 (4.70)	23.6 (4.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	36 (2)		n.a.		n.a.	
Vigorous-intensity physical activity [30 minutes/week]						
Median (IQR; range)	4.0 (7.0; 0-210)	3.0 (6.5; 0-155)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	328 (17.8)		n.a.		n.a.	
Moderate-intensity physical activity [30 minutes/week]						
Median (IQR; range)	4.0 (6.0; 0-224)	3.0 (6.0; 0-112)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	315 (17.1)		n.a.		n.a.	
Current health status						
Good-Excellent	1754 (95.0)	402 (22.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Fair-Poor	92 (5.0)	79 (85.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Supplemental Table S5. (continued)

Pain						
None-Mild	1669 (90.4)	361 (21.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Moderate-Very severe	175 (9.5)	120 (68.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	2 (0.1)		n.a.		n.a.	
Late effects						
Nr. of organ systems affected: ^a						
Median (IQR; range)	1 (2; 0-9)	2 (2; 0-9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
No	546 (29.6)	85 (15.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Any	1295 (70.2)	394 (30.4)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Neurological	617 (33.4)	240 (38.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Musculoskeletal	407 (22.0)	147 (36.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Cardiovascular	176 (9.5)	62 (35.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Vision	246 (13.3)	84 (34.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Hearing	207 (11.2)	85 (41.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Endocrine	248 (13.4)	95 (38.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Pulmonary	519 (28.1)	170 (32.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Digestive	266 (14.4)	117 (44.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Urinary	64 (3.5)	25 (39.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	5 (0.3)		n.a.		n.a.	
Psychological distress^c						
No	1566 (84.8)	286 (18.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	248 (13.4)	184 (74.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	32 (1.7)		n.a.		n.a.	
Diagnosis						
Leukaemia	493 (26.7)	123 (24.9)	189 (27.6)	54 (28.6)	n.a.	n.a.
Lymphoma	459 (24.9)	107 (23.3)	167 (24.4)	40 (24.0)	n.a.	n.a.
CNS tumour	276 (15.0)	96 (34.8)	73 (10.7)	36 (49.3)	n.a.	n.a.
Neuroblastoma	46 (2.5)	15 (32.6)	19 (2.8)	3 (15.8)	n.a.	n.a.
Retinoblastoma	25 (1.4)	5 (20.0)	10 (1.5)	4 (40.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Renal tumour	66 (3.6)	8 (12.1)	30 (4.4)	4 (13.3)	n.a.	n.a.
Hepatic tumour	11 (0.6)	1 (9.1)	3 (0.4)	. (.)	n.a.	n.a.
Malignant bone tumour	112 (6.1)	30 (26.8)	46 (6.7)	12 (26.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Soft tissue sarcoma	120 (6.5)	33 (27.5)	61 (8.9)	18 (29.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Germ cell tumour	124 (6.7)	29 (23.4)	40 (5.8)	12 (30.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Other tumour	66 (3.6)	22 (33.3)	29 (4.2)	10 (34.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Langerhans cell histiocytosis	48 (2.6)	12 (25.0)	17 (2.5)	5 (29.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Surgery						
No	529 (28.7)	137 (25.9)	200 (29.2)	54 (27.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	1229 (66.6)	311 (25.3)	448 (65.5)	129 (28.8)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	88 (4.8)		36 (5.3)		n.a.	
Chemotherapy						
No	376 (20.4)	116 (30.9)	117 (17.1)	45 (38.5)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	1372 (74.3)	336 (24.5)	526 (76.9)	136 (25.9)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	98 (5.3)		41 (6.0)		n.a.	
Radiotherapy						
No	1092 (59.2)	265 (24.3)	386 (56.4)	98 (25.4)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	641 (34.7)	180 (28.1)	254 (37.1)	83 (32.7)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	113 (6.1)		44 (6.4)		n.a.	
Stem cell transplantation						
No	1652 (89.5)	421 (25.5)	613 (89.6)	171 (27.9)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	59 (3.2)	16 (27.1)	15 (2.2)	6 (40.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	135 (7.3)		56 (8.2)		n.a.	
Relapse / SMN						
No	1492 (80.8)	390 (26.1)	557 (81.4)	161 (28.9)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	354 (19.2)	91 (25.7)	127 (18.6)	37 (29.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Age at diagnosis [years]						
Median (IQR; range)	12.0 (9.0; 0-20)	13.0 (9.0; 0-20)	10.0 (9.0; 0-20)	11.5 (9.0; 0-20)	n.a.	n.a.
Year of diagnosis						
1976-1985	453 (24.5)	102 (22.5)	228 (33.3)	61 (26.8)	n.a.	n.a.
1986-1995	687 (37.2)	172 (25.0)	299 (43.7)	90 (30.1)	n.a.	n.a.
1996-2005	413 (22.4)	114 (27.6)	149 (21.8)	45 (30.2)	n.a.	n.a.
2006-2015	293 (15.9)	93 (31.7)	8 (1.2)	2 (25.0)	n.a.	n.a.

Note: "Missing" is only displayed if there are missing values for the respective variable. Abbreviations: CNS=central nervous system, n.a.=not available, SD=standard deviation, SMN=second malignant neoplasm

* All variables (except age at study, time from baseline, time since diagnosis, and fatigue) were measured at baseline.

^a total percentage

^b row percentage

^c T-score \geq 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory BSI-18

Supplemental Table S6. *Fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score)

stratified by the characteristics of the study population.

	Survivors						General population		
	Baseline: N=1846			Follow-up: N=684*			N=863		
	Total Mean (SD)	Without fatigue Mean (SD)	With fatigue Mean (SD)	Total Mean (SD)	Without fatigue Mean (SD)	With fatigue Mean (SD)	Total Mean (SD)	Without fatigue Mean (SD)	With fatigue Mean (SD)
Sex									
Male	51.7 (10.4)	55.8 (6.9)	37.0 (6.3)	50.4 (10.5)	54.9 (6.7)	36.0 (6.7)	50.9 (9.5)	54.2 (6.2)	35.8 (7.5)
Female	48.6 (11.1)	54.4 (6.8)	35.3 (6.7)	47.5 (11.2)	54.1 (6.3)	34.9 (6.6)	48.2 (10.5)	54.0 (6.2)	35.8 (6.1)
Age at study [years]									
20-29 years	50.3 (10.6)	55.2 (6.8)	36.5 (6.4)	49.5 (11.6)	55.1 (7.5)	35.5 (7.3)	48.1 (10.2)	53.2 (6.5)	36.0 (6.3)
30-39 years	50.3 (10.8)	54.9 (6.9)	35.5 (6.7)	49.4 (10.5)	54.7 (6.2)	36.0 (6.4)	49.0 (9.7)	53.8 (6.0)	36.8 (5.6)
40-49 years	49.7 (12.0)	56.0 (7.6)	35.2 (6.5)	48.6 (11.2)	54.4 (6.6)	34.4 (6.9)	50.1 (9.1)	54.4 (5.9)	37.9 (4.5)
50-59 years	46.2 (14.0)	55.2 (6.0)	30.4 (8.7)	44.7 (10.7)	52.1 (5.6)	33.4 (5.0)	49.5 (11.5)	54.5 (6.4)	32.2 (8.0)
Time since diagnosis [years]									
5-14 years	49.5 (10.8)	54.8 (6.6)	36.0 (6.8)	47.3 (12.7)	55.3 (8.0)	34.7 (7.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
15-24 years	50.8 (10.5)	55.3 (7.0)	36.6 (5.9)	49.4 (10.3)	54.3 (6.4)	36.2 (6.4)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
25-34 years	50.4 (11.5)	55.6 (7.4)	35.4 (7.1)	48.7 (10.6)	54.3 (6.1)	35.4 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
35-44 years	47.9 (12.3)	54.6 (5.8)	31.3 (6.7)	49.9 (11.9)	55.5 (7.2)	34.0 (7.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Time from baseline [years]									
0-4 years	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	47.3 (11.5)	54.0 (6.7)	34.3 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
5-9 years	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	49.5 (10.8)	54.9 (6.5)	35.5 (6.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
10+ years	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	49.4 (7.9)	52.7 (6.0)	39.4 (3.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Language region									
German	51.3 (10.3)	55.4 (6.9)	36.7 (6.5)	50.1 (10.3)	54.7 (6.3)	35.9 (6.5)	50.0 (9.8)	54.2 (6.0)	35.9 (6.3)
French	47.8 (11.4)	54.5 (6.9)	35.1 (6.5)	46.2 (11.9)	54.3 (7.1)	34.8 (6.7)	46.0 (10.7)	52.9 (6.8)	36.0 (6.6)
Italian	47.0 (12.3)	55.1 (7.7)	35.4 (7.1)	48.0 (12.2)	53.4 (6.9)	30.4 (8.1)	52.6 (9.8)	55.2 (6.0)	33.7 (11.7)
Missing	n=14 (0.8%)			n=0 (0.0%)			n=0 (0.0%)		
Migration background									
No	50.9 (10.4)	55.4 (6.9)	36.8 (6.1)	49.5 (10.6)	54.5 (6.5)	35.6 (6.8)	49.5 (10.1)	54.1 (6.1)	35.7 (6.8)
Yes	47.2 (12.1)	54.5 (6.7)	33.8 (7.1)	46.8 (11.6)	54.9 (6.6)	34.9 (5.6)	48.6 (10.3)	53.9 (6.5)	36.1 (5.6)
Missing	n=93 (5.0%)			n=29 (4.2%)			n=0 (0.0%)		
Civil status									
Single	50.1 (10.6)	55.0 (6.8)	36.3 (6.5)	49.0 (10.8)	54.4 (6.4)	35.5 (6.7)	48.9 (10.2)	54.0 (6.0)	35.6 (6.5)
Married	50.9 (11.1)	55.6 (7.3)	35.7 (6.5)	49.3 (10.9)	55.0 (6.8)	36.2 (5.7)	49.6 (9.8)	54.0 (6.2)	36.5 (6.1)
Widowed/Divorced	50.5 (12.8)	56.8 (7.0)	33.0 (8.2)	48.2 (14.5)	55.1 (6.5)	24.7 (6.5)	48.9 (11.6)	54.8 (6.5)	33.8 (7.2)
Missing	n=23 (1.2%)			n=6 (0.9%)			n=40 (4.6%)		
Educational achievement									
Compulsory school	47.2 (12.6)	55.6 (7.1)	34.3 (7.2)	45.8 (12.9)	54.6 (7.6)	33.7 (7.7)	46.1 (13.9)	56.3 (7.7)	32.7 (7.1)
Vocational training	50.7 (10.5)	55.1 (6.9)	36.2 (6.5)	49.7 (10.7)	54.9 (6.6)	35.7 (6.2)	49.2 (10.2)	53.9 (6.0)	35.2 (6.7)
Upper secondary									
education	51.1 (10.4)	55.6 (6.9)	37.0 (6.2)	49.2 (10.0)	54.3 (5.3)	35.8 (6.2)	49.2 (9.5)	53.6 (5.7)	36.6 (6.4)
University education	49.2 (10.4)	54.6 (6.6)	36.5 (6.0)	47.3 (11.4)	52.5 (7.3)	33.6 (8.3)	50.2 (9.6)	54.4 (6.4)	37.2 (5.1)
Missing	n=36 (2.0%)			n=8 (1.2%)			n=44 (5.1%)		
Employment status									
Employed	50.8 (10.4)	55.2 (6.9)	36.6 (6.3)	49.5 (10.6)	54.5 (6.3)	35.1 (6.7)	49.7 (9.7)	54.1 (6.2)	36.5 (5.6)
Unemployed	46.1 (13.1)	55.0 (7.9)	33.2 (6.8)	42.9 (11.5)	53.9 (5.8)	34.7 (6.9)	45.8 (13.5)	54.8 (6.8)	32.4 (9.1)
In education	49.3 (10.6)	54.8 (6.6)	36.6 (6.3)	49.5 (10.7)	55.0 (7.4)	37.3 (5.0)	49.2 (9.9)	53.1 (5.8)	34.7 (8.0)
Missing	n=60 (3.3%)			n=20 (2.9%)			n=21 (2.4%)		
Fatigue prevalence									
No	55.2 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	54.5 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.	54.1 (6.2)	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	36.0 (6.6)	n.a.	n.a.	35.3 (6.6)	n.a.	n.a.	35.8 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.
BMI									
<18	46.3 (10.5)	52.1 (5.4)	34.6 (8.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
18-24	50.8 (10.5)	55.3 (7.0)	36.6 (6.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
25-29	50.2 (11.0)	55.4 (6.7)	35.7 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
>30	47.7 (11.8)	54.3 (7.2)	34.6 (7.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=36 (2.0%)			n.a.			n.a.		
Time spent on vigorous-intensity physical activity [minutes/week]									
Below average									
(<120)	48.4 (11.1)	54.4 (6.7)	35.3 (6.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Above average									
(120+)	51.9 (10.5)	55.8 (7.0)	36.3 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=328 (17.8%)			n.a.			n.a.		

Supplemental Table S6. (continued)

Time spent on moderate-intensity physical activity [minutes/week]									
Below average									
(<120)	49.3 (11.0)	54.9 (6.8)	35.9 (6.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Above average									
(120+)	51.2 (10.5)	55.4 (7.0)	36.0 (6.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=315 (17.1%)			n.a.			n.a.		
Current health status									
Good-Excellent	51.1 (10.1)	55.2 (6.9)	37.2 (5.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Fair-Poor	32.9 (10.1)	49.5 (4.9)	30.1 (7.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Pain									
None-Mild	51.5 (9.9)	55.4 (6.9)	37.4 (5.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Moderate-Very severe	37.9 (11.2)	50.9 (5.2)	32.0 (7.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=2 (0.1%)			n.a.			n.a.		
Late effects									
None	53.5 (10.1)	56.6 (7.2)	36.6 (6.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
At least one	48.8 (10.8)	54.4 (6.6)	35.9 (6.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Neurological	46.6 (11.5)	54.0 (6.7)	35.0 (7.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Musculoskeletal	47.1 (11.2)	54.0 (6.3)	35.0 (6.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Cardiovascular	47.2 (12.1)	54.5 (6.6)	33.9 (7.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Vision	47.5 (11.4)	54.1 (6.8)	34.8 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Hearing	45.7 (11.5)	53.5 (6.5)	34.4 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Endocrine	46.2 (11.2)	53.2 (6.6)	34.8 (6.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Pulmonary	48.2 (10.7)	54.1 (6.6)	36.2 (6.4)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Digestive	45.4 (11.8)	54.0 (6.2)	34.4 (7.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Urinary	45.4 (10.3)	52.5 (4.4)	34.5 (6.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=5 (0.3%)			n.a.			n.a.		
Psychological distress^a									
No	52.2 (9.6)	55.4 (6.9)	37.7 (5.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	37.8 (9.6)	50.2 (4.9)	33.5 (6.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=32 (1.7%)			n.a.			n.a.		
Diagnosis									
Leukaemia	50.9 (10.5)	55.6 (6.7)	36.7 (6.1)	49.7 (10.0)	54.7 (6.0)	37.0 (5.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Lymphoma	51.0 (10.6)	55.5 (7.1)	36.4 (6.1)	50.3 (10.4)	54.9 (6.8)	36.0 (5.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
CNS tumour	48.2 (10.9)	54.5 (6.9)	36.4 (6.2)	43.9 (12.6)	54.3 (5.9)	33.1 (7.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Neuroblastoma	48.6 (13.6)	55.8 (8.3)	33.6 (9.7)	52.9 (10.8)	56.3 (7.9)	34.9 (3.6)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Retinoblastoma	52.2 (10.1)	56.0 (6.7)	36.6 (3.8)	45.5 (9.3)	51.3 (5.0)	36.7 (7.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Renal tumour	53.9 (9.6)	56.3 (7.2)	36.3 (5.8)	51.1 (8.1)	53.4 (5.1)	35.8 (7.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Hepatic tumour	46.8 (10.7)	49.9 (4.0)	16.7 ^b	56.8 (3.6)	56.8 (3.6)	0.0 (0.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Malignant bone tumour	49.3 (11.0)	54.6 (6.3)	34.8 (7.3)	48.5 (11.6)	53.7 (7.3)	33.7 (8.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Soft tissue sarcoma	49.8 (10.3)	54.6 (6.6)	37.3 (7.1)	48.7 (11.2)	54.2 (7.0)	35.5 (7.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Germ cell tumour	49.6 (12.2)	54.9 (7.2)	32.3 (8.2)	48.4 (11.6)	54.2 (7.9)	34.9 (6.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Other tumour	47.6 (9.8)	53.3 (5.9)	36.1 (4.7)	47.5 (12.8)	55.6 (5.8)	32.0 (5.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Langerhans cell histiocytosis	50.1 (10.7)	54.8 (7.0)	35.8 (6.2)	49.1 (9.3)	53.7 (6.4)	37.8 (3.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Surgery									
No	50.7 (10.6)	55.6 (6.9)	36.7 (6.2)	49.9 (10.2)	54.9 (6.1)	36.6 (6.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	50.2 (10.8)	55.1 (7.0)	35.9 (6.6)	48.7 (11.0)	54.3 (6.6)	35.0 (6.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=88 (4.8%)			n=36 (5.3%)			n.a.		
Chemotherapy									
No	48.8 (11.0)	54.5 (7.1)	36.0 (6.7)	46.2 (11.8)	53.9 (6.2)	33.9 (7.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	50.7 (10.7)	55.4 (6.9)	36.2 (6.4)	49.8 (10.4)	54.6 (6.5)	36.0 (6.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=98 (5.3%)			n=41 (6.0%)			n.a.		
Radiotherapy									
No	50.7 (10.7)	55.3 (6.9)	36.1 (6.8)	49.7 (10.5)	54.6 (6.4)	35.5 (6.4)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	49.7 (10.8)	55.0 (7.1)	36.2 (6.0)	48.2 (11.1)	54.3 (6.6)	35.5 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=113 (6.1%)			n=44 (6.4%)			n.a.		
Stem cell transplantation									
No	50.3 (10.8)	55.2 (6.9)	36.0 (6.6)	49.2 (10.8)	54.5 (6.4)	35.4 (6.7)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	50.4 (10.6)	55.3 (7.5)	37.2 (4.8)	45.8 (9.9)	52.3 (6.3)	36.1 (5.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Missing	n=135 (7.3%)			n=56 (8.2%)			n.a.		
Relapse/SMN									
No	50.3 (10.8)	55.3 (6.8)	36.1 (6.7)	49.1 (10.9)	54.6 (6.5)	35.4 (6.5)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Yes	49.8 (10.8)	54.7 (7.3)	35.8 (6.2)	48.5 (11.0)	54.1 (6.6)	34.9 (7.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Age at diagnosis [years]									
0-5 years	51.2 (10.3)	55.3 (6.9)	36.7 (6.4)	50.5 (9.8)	54.3 (6.2)	36.2 (6.9)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
6-10 years	50.3 (11.2)	55.5 (7.4)	35.8 (6.1)	48.9 (11.2)	55.1 (6.4)	35.4 (6.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
11-15 years	50.1 (11.0)	55.2 (7.0)	36.0 (6.8)	48.7 (11.3)	55.0 (6.9)	35.6 (6.2)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
16-20 years	49.2 (10.7)	54.6 (6.4)	35.7 (6.8)	47.1 (11.3)	53.4 (6.4)	33.8 (7.0)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Supplemental Table S6. (continued)

Year of diagnosis									
1976-1985	51.4 (11.3)	56.0 (7.5)	35.5 (6.6)	49.5 (11.5)	55.1 (6.7)	34.1 (7.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
1986-1995	50.3 (10.4)	55.0 (6.8)	36.4 (6.1)	48.4 (9.9)	53.6 (5.8)	36.3 (6.1)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
1996-2005	49.6 (10.9)	54.9 (6.7)	35.7 (7.0)	49.6 (11.7)	55.7 (7.2)	35.5 (6.8)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
2006-2015	48.8 (10.7)	54.6 (6.3)	36.4 (6.8)	45.8 (13.3)	51.9 (7.2)	27.6 (10.3)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Note: Standardized scores range from 0 to 100, with lower scores indicating greater fatigue (fatigue severity). Abbreviations: CNS=central nervous system, BSI-18= Brief Symptom Inventory-18, n.a.=not available, SMN=second malignant neoplasm

* All variables (except age at study, time from baseline, time since diagnosis, and fatigue) were measured at baseline.

^a T-score \geq 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory BSI-18

^b Only one observation in this category, calculation of SD therefore omitted

Supplemental Table S7. Frequency of specific longitudinal patterns of fatigue in survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer, and corresponding *fatigue severity* (SF-36 vitality scale score), and *fatigue prevalence* and *severity* in the general population.

	Survivors		General population		
	Baseline	Follow-up	Fatigue prevalence	Fatigue severity	
	<i>Fatigue severity</i>	<i>Fatigue severity</i>	<i>Fatigue prevalence</i>	<i>Fatigue severity</i>	
	n (%)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	n (%) ^a	Mean (SD) ^a
No/low fatigue	437 (63.9)	56.0 (6.8)	55.0 (6.5)	638 (73.9)	54.1 (6.2)
Late onset fatigue	93 (13.6)	52.4 (6.3)	37.0 (6.1)	n.a.	n.a.
Improving fatigue	49 (7.2)	38.6 (4.6)	50.8 (5.0)	n.a.	n.a.
Persistent fatigue	105 (15.3)	35.6 (6.3)	33.8 (6.8)	225 (26.1)	35.8 (6.5)

^a Fatigue was only assessed at one timepoint for participants from the general population. Those who experienced fatigue are displayed in the *persistent fatigue* category, and those without in the *no/low fatigue* category.

Supplemental Table S8. Baseline characteristics associated with persistent fatigue (from univariable logistic regression).

	n=	Persistent fatigue (vs. no/low fatigue)			
		OR	95% CI		p-value
Diagnosis	539				
Leukaemia		Ref.			
Lymphoma		0.87	0.47	1.64	0.670
CNS tumour		3.19	1.59	6.39	0.001
Other tumour		0.97	0.55	1.70	0.919
Treatment					
Surgery (Ref. No)	511	1.19	0.72	1.96	0.504
Chemotherapy (Ref. No)	506	0.48	0.29	0.81	0.006
Radiotherapy (Ref. No)	502	1.41	0.89	2.23	0.141
Stem cell transplantation (Ref. No)	492	2.70	0.77	9.43	0.120
Relapse/SMN: Yes (Ref. No)	542	1.05	0.62	1.79	0.856
Age at diagnosis [continuous]	542	1.06	1.02	1.10	0.003
Year of diagnosis	537				
1976-1985		Ref.			
1986-1995		1.11	0.68	1.84	0.672
1996-2005		1.37	0.78	2.42	0.275
2006-2015		n.a. ^c			
Time since diagnosis: [years]	542	1.01	0.98	1.05	0.363
Health status: Fair-Poor (Ref. Good-Excellent)	542	54.38	12.51	236.27	<0.001
Late effects: Number^a	541	1.73	1.49	2.02	<0.001
Late effects, any (Ref. No)	541	3.26	1.85	5.74	<0.001
Neurological (Ref. No)	538	3.91	2.51	6.11	<0.001
Musculoskeletal (Ref. No)	540	2.00	1.25	3.21	0.004
Cardiovascular (Ref. No)	535	1.97	1.01	3.84	0.048
Vision (Ref. No)	537	3.09	1.74	5.48	<0.001
Hearing (Ref. No)	533	1.93	1.03	3.62	0.042
Endocrine (Ref. No)	537	3.02	1.77	5.17	<0.001
Pulmonary (Ref. No)	536	1.31	0.82	2.09	0.253
Digestive (Ref. No)	535	4.42	2.60	7.50	<0.001
Urinary (Ref. No)	536	3.32	1.36	8.09	0.008
Psychological distress:^b Yes (Ref. No)	538	22.88	11.84	44.22	<0.001
Pain: Moderate-Very severe (Ref. None-Mild)	542	15.53	7.65	31.53	<0.001
BMI [continuous]	537	1.06	1.02	1.11	0.009
Vigorous-intensity physical activity [30 minutes/week]	491	0.98	0.96	1.00	0.047
Moderate-intensity physical activity [30 minutes/week]	486	0.97	0.94	1.00	0.051
Year of study participation: [year]	542	1.18	1.08	1.28	<0.001
Age at study: [years]	542	1.05	1.02	1.08	0.001
Sex: Female (Ref. Male)	542	1.56	1.02	2.39	0.042
Civil status	537				
Single		Ref.			
Married		1.11	0.67	1.84	0.695
Divorced/Widowed		1.16	0.37	3.59	0.801
Educational achievement	536				
Compulsory school		0.95	0.31	1.59	0.003
Vocational training		Ref.			
Upper secondary education		0.21	-0.35	0.76	0.467
University education		0.39	-0.37	1.16	0.312
Employment situation	528				
Employed		Ref.			
Unemployed		4.21	2.07	8.58	<0.001
In education		1.35	0.70	2.63	0.370

Note: Bold font indicates results with p-values <0.05. Abbreviations: BMI=body mass index, CI=confidence interval, CNS=central nervous system, OR=odds ratio, SMN=second malignant neoplasm

^a number of organ systems affected by late effects (neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive, or urinary)

^b T-score ≥ 63 on at least two dimensions or the Global Severity Index of the Brief Symptom Inventory BSI-18

^c Predicts fatigue pattern perfectly, observations not used.

Appendix 1. Detailed information on coding and scoring of explanatory variables from the SCCSS and the general population

- **Year of diagnosis:** We recoded year of diagnosis into 10-year categories (1976-1985, 1986-1995, 1996-2005, 2006-2015).
- **Health status:** Current health status was assessed with one item of the SF-36 (“In general, would you say your health is: 1 – Excellent; 2 - Very good; 3 – Good; 4 – Fair; 5 – Poor”) and recoded into “good-excellent” for scores 1-3 and “fair-poor” for scores 4-5. We scored the SF-36 with subscales according to the scoring manual.¹
- **Organ-specific late effects:** Prevalence of specific late effects was assessed by asking survivors whether they currently experienced specific health conditions of different organ systems (yes, no): neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive, or urinary. For each organ system, we coded prevalence “yes” if participants endorsed at least one of the specific health conditions assessed. Participants who answered “no” or who left a question blank were included in the “no” categories.² If participants did not complete any question on health conditions, they were coded to have missing information.
- **Any late effects:** We generated an “any prevalence of late effects” variable coding “yes” if a late effect of any organ system (neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive, or urinary) was prevalent.
- **Number of organ systems affected by late effects:** We generated a variable “number of organ systems affected by late effects” by counting how many organ systems were affected by late effects for each participant (possible range: 0-9 organ systems (neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, vision, hearing, endocrine, pulmonary, digestive, or urinary)).

- **Psychological distress:** We standardized the BSI-18 summary scores into T-Scores (scores with a mean of 50 and standard deviation of 10) according to Franke et al. (2017) and Michel et al. (2024), with higher scores indicating higher severity of symptoms.^{3,4}
- **Pain:** Pain was assessed with one item of the SF-36 (“How much bodily pain have you had during the past 4 weeks? 1 – None; 2 – Very mild; 3 – Mild; 4 – Moderate; 5 – Severe”; 6 – Very severe”) and recoded into “none-mild” for scores 1-3 and “moderate-very severe” for scores 4-6. We scored the SF-36 with subscales according to the scoring manual.¹
- **Physical activity** was assessed by asking participants about their average time (total minutes per week) spent on doing vigorous (e.g. running, cycling, etc.) and moderate (e.g. walking, dancing, etc.) activities.
- **Migration background:** We coded survivors as having a migration background if they were not born in Switzerland, were not a Swiss citizen, or were not a Swiss citizen since birth.

References

- 1 Morfeld M, Kirchberger I, Bullinger M. SF-36 Fragebogen zum Gesundheitszustand. Deutsche Version des Short Form-36 Health Survey. Göttingen: Hogrefe, 2011.
- 2 Belle FN, Sláma T, Schindera C, et al. Body image in adolescent survivors of childhood cancer: The role of chronic health conditions. *Pediatric Blood & Cancer* 2022; e29958. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pbc.29958>.
- 3 Michel G, Baenziger J, Brodbeck J, Mader L, Kuehni CE, Roser K. The Brief Symptom Inventory in the Swiss general population: Presentation of norm scores and predictors of psychological distress. *PLoS One* 2024; **19**: e0305192. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0305192>.
- 4 Franke GH, Jaeger S, Glaesmer H, Barkmann C, Petrowski K, Braehler E. Psychometric analysis of the brief symptom inventory 18 (BSI-18) in a representative German sample. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 2017; **17**: 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-016-0283-3>.